

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

GPC5 (glypican 5)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	2262 / P78333
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
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Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: Human GPC5 (E25-E548). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.93 (rank #494, 98th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.93 out of 5 (rank #494, 98th percentile). The individual score components include 1.96 of 3 for genetics, and 1.97 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of GPC5 protein is significantly increased and RNA is significantly decreased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. GPC5 is annotated to GO terms from the Structural Stabilization, Proteostasis, and Endolysosome domains.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
3.929	494	98.02	1.964	1.965

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of

expression. The expression of GPC5 is confidently detected in astrocytes, vascular and leptomenigeal cells (VLMC), oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPC), oligodendrocytes, and both excitatory and inhibitory sub-types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Glypican 5, a heparan sulfate proteoglycan, was identified in deep brain proteomic studies of AD associated with cognitive and pathological traits (1). While there is little direct evidence suggesting a role for GPC5 in AD pathogenesis, there are interesting links between GPC5, heparan sulfate proteoglycan biology, and AD

that suggest a plausible role (see discussion in next section). The goal of this project is to develop resources for the scientific community to study GPC5 more effectively through the development of a target enabling package (TEP) set of resources. The GPC5 TEP will include identification of validated antibodies, purified protein and a bioinformatic analysis for the target to facilitate future studies by the academic and pharmaceutical communities. We hope this will help advance the study of this potential disease associated target and clarify the role of GPC5 in AD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Glypican 5 (GPC5) is a member of the heparan sulfate proteoglycan family, and consequently involves a heavily glycosaminoglycan (GAGs), in this case heparin, conjugation and membrane association with the exterior of the cell (2-4). GPC5 was originally identified as a developmental factor expressed in numerous tissues including brain (2-4). The heparin proteoglycan family, including GPC5, interact with many extracellular matrix proteins and are known to play anticoagulatory roles by blocking association of cells with thrombin factors and other elements of the coagulation cascade (5-8). Similarly, the negatively charged heparin molecules play an immune-modulatory role by regulating interaction with cytokines and other growth factor proteins (8-10). GPC5 can also interfere with receptor mediated signalling cascades blocking, for example, classes of Wnt mediated signalling (11, 12). The blockade of Wnt-signalling suppresses some forms of tumor progression, which is the mechanism through which GPC5 maintains at least some of its tumor suppressor function (11, 13), although other mechanisms employing regulation of exosome secretion and alternative signalling pathways have been proposed(14).

The mechanistic connections between GPC5 and AD is unknown but could involve the role of GPC5 in regulating cell cycle progression and neoplastic activity in both development and cancer models, as cell cycle dysregulation is suggested in AD(15, 16). GPC5 was identified in deep brain proteomic studies of AD as part of Module 42 (M42) which is a set of upregulated proteins that are strongly correlated with both cognitive decline and pathological development in AD brains (1). GPC5, as a member of the heparin proteoglycan family, could be a direct modulator of amyloid biogenesis or Tau fibrillation, as there are reported mechanisms linking heparin with modulation of both pathologies (17-19). In the case of amyloid production, heparin is reported to alter beta-secretase mediated pathological proteolysis of APP(18), and tethering heparin to proteoglycans in the extracellular milieu could also prevent amyloid plaque formation, as heparin is linked with complex oligomeric amyloid production (19-21). Additionally, heparin interacts with the R3 domain within Tau (22), and may facilitate fibril formation, aggregation and the alteration of microtubule mediated trafficking. These are all hypothetical mechanisms for potential disease-state linkage but could be involved in the association of GPC5 with AD pathogenesis. We hope that the TEP resources produced will facilitate a clarification of whether and how GPC5 is involved in AD.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

1. GPC5A-c001: Human GPC5 (E25-E548). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further investigation of the role of GPC5 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. GPC5A-c001: Human GPC5 (E25-E548). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

Construct ID	GPC5A-c001
Parental vector	pHL-avitag3
Tag	C-terminal His6, C-terminal Avitag
Protein mass (with tag and secretion signal)	65287.4 Da
Extinction Coefficient ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	53860
Protein sequence (with tag)	MGILPSPGMPALLSLVSLLSVLLMGCVAETGEGVQTCEEVRKLFQWRLLGAVRGLPDSRA GPDQLQVCISKKPTCCTRKMEERYQIARQDMQQFLQTSSTLKFILSRNAAAFQETLELIQ AENYTSILFCSTYRNMALEAAASVQEFTDVGlyLFGADVNPeeFVNRFFDSLFPlyVNHlin PGVTDSSLEYSECIRMARRDVSPFGNIPQRVMGQMGRSLLPSRTFLQALNLGIEVINTTDYL HFSKECSRALLKMQYCPHCQGLALTKPCMGYCLNVMRGCLAHMAELNPHWHAYIRSLEEL SDAMHGTYDIGHVLLNFHLLVNDAVLQAHLNGQKLEQVNRICGRPVRTPTQSPRCsFDQs KEKHGMKTTTRNSEETLANRRKEFINSLRlyRSFYGGladQLCanelAAADGLPCWNGEDI VKSyTQRVVGNGIKAQSGNPEVKVKGIDPVINQIIdKlKHVVQLLQGRSPKPKDWELLQLGS GGGMVEQVSGDCDDEDGCGGSGSgeVkrTLKITDWMPPDDMNFSDVKQIHQTDTGSTLD TTGAGTGGSGSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGRTKHHHHHH

Purified Protein	
Size Exclusion Chromatography: GPC5A-c001 (with tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: GPC5A-c001 (with tag)	N/A
Observed Mass:	N/A
Protein yield:	0.4mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>Mammalian</i> : Expi293F cells (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Expression medium	FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Plasmid purification	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain MACH1. Plate on LB-agar plates containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml). Inoculate 5 ml LB broth containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml) with a single colony and grow 6h at 37°C with shaking. Inoculate 800 ml LB broth containing the same antibiotic with 2 ml of starter culture and grow overnight at

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	37°C with shaking. Split culture into 4 and perform MaxiPrep (Qiagen) with 4 columns according to manufacturer's instructions. Add 0.7 volumes of isopropanol to precipitate the plasmid. Spin (17000g, 30 min, 4°C) and wash pellet with 70% ethanol. Resuspend plasmid with sterile TE buffer under sterile conditions. Yield is typically 2 mg of plasmid.
Transfection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Split Expi293F cells to 1×10^6 cells/ml in 1L FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium. Incubate for 24 h until cells are approximately 2×10^6 cells/ml (37°C, 150 rpm, 8% CO₂, 75% rh). 2. Add plasmid to 20mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 0.5 µg/ml final concentration. 3. Add linear PEI (1 mg/ml sterile stock) to another 20mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 3 µg/ml final concentration. 4. Add the mixture from Step 3 to the one in Step 2 and incubate at room temperature for 30 min. 5. Add the plasmid/PEI mixture slowly to the cells. 6. Add sodium butyrate (1 M sterile stock) to 12 mM final concentration. 7. Incubate cells at 30°C (8%CO₂/75% rh) with shaking at 150 rpm. 8. Harvest cell culture supernatant at 5 days post transfection (900g, 20 min, 4°C). 9. Filter supernatant through 0.2 µm filter.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ni IMAC W10 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 2. Ni IMAC W25 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 25 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 3. Ni IMAC elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, 2% glycerol 4. Size exclusion chromatography elution buffer : dPBS (from ThermoFisher) 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Ni IMAC W10 buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add imidazole to filtered supernatant to 10 mM final concentration. 2. Add a total of 2.5 ml equilibrated Ni-sepharose beads to the cell supernatant, split into 50-ml falcon tubes. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 3. Spin beads/supernatant slurry (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant supernatant and wash beads with 100 ml W10 buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml W10. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 4. Wash column with 25 ml W25. 5. Elute protein with 1x 10 ml elution buffer, followed by 2x5 ml elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. Pool elution fractions containing protein.
Purification step 2: Size Exclusion Chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate pooled IMAC elution fractions to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Perform SEC on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column, equilibrated in DPBS, at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 1-5 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

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